

TOPLAP Barcelona Community Report 2023

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SUMMARY

Barcelona has developed an active community of live coders. This report traces back the history and development of the TOPLAP Barcelona node, from its predecessors and roots, through its founding as a collective, to the present day. In addition, it presents its ongoing activities and how they shape the character of the community as we can see it today.

1 History

1.1 Roots

TOPLAP Barcelona emerged from diverse practices and communities that existed before the association was officially founded in 2018. A mix of academics, do-it-yourselfers and otherwise “unaffiliated” music and technology aficionados developed tools, held workshops and put on concerts, exploring a wide range of sound and visual practices. Many of them embraced computer coding as an explicit artistic gesture. People and practices gathered and dispersed, coming from many places to coalesce and form the core of the new community.

It is worth mentioning the work of *l'ull cec* (conceived by Sam Roig), organizing experimental concerts and workshops. *L'ull cec* brought the city many of its first live coding workshops, ranging from *ixi-lang* to granular synthesis and machine learning in SuperCollider, as well as the first *TidalCycles* workshop. The SuperCollider users group met every first Tuesday of the month, usually with free-form meetings that welcomed experienced users and novices alike.

The *Barcelona Laptop Orchestra*, founded around 2008 by Alex Barrachina and Josep Maria Comajuncosas at the sonology department of the Escola Superior de Música de Catalunya, performed with collective musical instruments built using code. The orchestra gathered people interested in electro-acoustic music, music technology and algorithmic composition.

The *Orquesta del Caos*, a multi-disciplinary collective that embraces sound art and experimental music, with an extensive track record of concerts and events, was one of the first local organizations interested in live coding. They organized a live coding concert in 2013 as part of the Zeppelin festival, held at the CCCB¹. This event also prompted the organization of the first local algorave, held at Freedomia in 2013.

Before the official founding of the collective, there were three algoraves. The first one was organized by Lina Bautista after the *live.code.festival* (which was held in Karlsruhe) on December 1, 2013. At the time, she had a group called *Codetroller*, arguably one of the first live coding groups in Barcelona. The other two were organized in October, 2016, and July, 2017, in collaboration with Iván Paz, and Niklas Reppel, who moved from Karlsruhe to Barcelona at the start 2017. The last of the three happened in conjunction with a *TidalCycles* workshop by Alexandra Cárdenas. These events were key moments that created the foundations of what would later become the TOPLAP Barcelona residency at Hangar, a centre for art research and production. Apart from live coders performing music and visuals, these events also featured people using modular synths (Barcelona has a strong modular synth community).

¹<https://www.cccb.org/en/activities/file/zeppelincomprimit2013/219800>

Figure 1: First Three Algorave Posters.

Around the time these algoraves happened, a generational change took place that led to the thriving community of live coders we find in Barcelona today. As some people left or shifted their interests, others entered the scene from around the world, or just *a la volta de la cantonada* (around the corner), bringing with them a diversity of experiences and views on live coding (not to mention art, music, and life in general).

1.2 Founding & Growth

In the late spring of 2018, Iván Paz and Lina Bautista officially founded *TOPLAP Barcelona*. When planning the initial activities they decided to clone the format of the *From Scratch* sessions held at the Centro Multimedia of Mexico City (Villasenor and Paz 2020).

At 7pm on May 31, 2018, TOPLAP Barcelona held its first official event with a *From Scratch* session at Sala Ricson of Hangar², where earlier that month the association earned a spot as a collective-in-residence (later, in early 2020, *TOPLAP Barcelona* became a registered cultural association). With the residency came access to the facilities, which allowed us to stage regular events and meetups, some of which, such as the *From Scratch* events, remain a monthly staple of the local scene.

The *From Scratch* events gave a low-threshold opportunity for people to try out their live coding skills in front of a benevolent audience, and became a fixture for regulars and a first point of contact for newcomers to the community. At the beginning of 2019, after the ICLC in Madrid, the first VIU Livecoding Festival was held at Hangar, bringing live coders from all over the world to Barcelona.

1.3 The Pandemic

When the COVID lockdown started in Barcelona (and almost everywhere else) in mid-March 2020, many of us entered a strange period of uncertainty and anxiety. To make things worse, although we were physically as close as ever, we were all suddenly isolated; it was no longer possible to gather in groups to share algoraves, workshops or our monthly *From Scratch* live-coding events, and it wouldn't be for many months.

Coincidentally, during the first week of lockdown there was a scheduled worldwide *EulerRoom Equinox* event, celebrating the 16th anniversary of TOPLAP. The Barcelona contingent had planned to gather and stream our block of performances together from the Hangar art centre on March 20. The pandemic situation meant that instead, we had to perform each from our respective homes. Nonetheless, this turned out to be a meaningful time of connection, listening to and watching live-coding streams while commenting and joking in the live chat. It was a perfect distraction from the frightening COVID news. We learned both how to share our online performances in this way, and that we desperately *needed* to.

All over Barcelona, during those first pandemic months, people went out onto their balconies at 8 p.m. every evening to clap for five minutes, applauding the health-care and other front-line workers who were dealing with the pandemic amidst such difficult conditions. The Barcelona TOPLAP community is all about applause (“clap-clap!”). Our *From*

²<https://www.hangar.org>

Figure 2: *Down The Rabbit Hole* cover. (Design: Citlali Hernández and Roger Pibernat)

Scratch sessions impose the requirement that everyone applaud after nine minutes, regardless of what happens. At that time, this gesture seemed more meaningful than ever.

From the end of March and throughout April 2020, we initiated a series of daily, live-streamed performances, each one featuring a different performer, giving a spot to everyone in our local TOPLAP community who wanted to prepare and live code a longer set. These streams started just as the nightly applause ended, and so were named *8:08: La hora del LIVECODER*. The first “batch” of these performances ran for three weeks (with fifteen local-but-remote performances), and later in May there was a second “season” with actually-remote invited guest performers from Mexico, Germany, the Netherlands, Canada and Spain.

The flurry of online activity in the first few months of the pandemic also included a series of workshops, each presented by a community member or invited guest. In addition, during the pandemic we collaborated on a compilation of live-coded tracks called *Down the Rabbit Hole*³, which is an acoustic snapshot of the community in 2020 and 2021. For many of our members, it turned out that live coding, learning, thinking and talking about live coding, and even making jokes about live coding were all excellent ways to avoid collapsing into a knot of anxiety in an increasingly uncertain world.

2 The Community Today

Thanks to a multitude of streaming activities, the community held out during times of lockdown, and emerged stronger than ever after Barcelona (earlier than many other places) reopened its cultural landscape. At first, this was into a hybrid state, where events had both a physical and online/streaming presence, and this helped hone people’s skills in staging this type of event.

As the pandemic slowly began to fade out, the four-year residency at Hangar came to an end as well, and the community had to move headquarters. A new office was quickly found, but when it came to booking concert spaces, a reorganization was needed. Luckily, at this point the community had developed enough to adapt to change, and in fact, being forced to look for new spaces and opportunities has helped us branch out and find new playgrounds.

What remains is an active, polyglot community of live coders, musicians, visualists, developers and organizers, with many interfaces to Barcelona’s rich environment of music and technology communities, including the modular synth and university research worlds.

2.1 Social Geographies

When considering the idea of *displacement* (a main theme of ICLC 2023), in the context of TOPLAP Barcelona, it is hard to ignore a particular feature of the Barcelona community: its members come from wide-ranging social geographies (understanding a social geography to be a set of relationships between persons and space). Barcelona is a city that attracts people from around the world, so the community is composed of people from countries as diverse as (in no

³<https://callitanythingrecords.bandcamp.com/album/down-the-rabbit-hole>

Figure 3: A Selection of Our Beloved Stickers

particular order) Mexico, Colombia, the USA, Germany, Argentina, Canada, and many more, obviously including Catalonia and Spain. This translates into a polyglot community in terms of programming and human languages, practices and symbolisms that form the identity of the community.

Food and drink is necessary to sustain live coders. Sharing *chupitos* of Mezcal (symbolizing the Mexican influence on the local community) is a tradition at our *algoraves*, sometimes jokingly as “punishment” for resorting to random number generators. The annual celebration of the harvest and eating of *calçots* (a type of green onion) in Catalonia was celebrated by a *Calçotada Web Audio* event during the /* VIU */ festival in 2020, with the following announcement:

“We’ll talk a bit about Web Audio technology and introduce some related instruments, then we’ll make some music with them while having vermut and calçots. We’ll also burn anything you bring! Not the laptops! that you can also bring.”

Other geographic features to mention are social/digital spaces. These reflect the community identity, solidified during the traditional *birra* (beer) after/during each *From Scratch* session. For example in the *Algorithmic-Barcelona* Telegram channel (the community’s main communication channel), frequently-shared stickers (designed by Roger Pibernat, one of the “locals”) include: a rooster holding a sign that says: *Queremo un workshop* (“we wanna workshop”), a bunny that claims: “rabbit holes are for rabbits,” or a rat that says: “the rat does not trust,” which is wordplay on the name of the Catalan herbal drink *Ratafia* (see Figure 3). All of them were born as jokes (the alarm marking the end of a nine-minute *From Scratch* session had a rooster sound) that found memetic expression in our digital spaces.

Another example worth mentioning is the deluge of cat-GIFs that populate the Telegram group. They started as an internal joke based on the assumption that cats are the most common image on the Internet, and have become part of our digital identity (although dog-lovers and non-pet-people are just as welcome).

3 Frequent Activities

3.1 From Scratch

As mentioned in (Villasenor and Paz 2020), “the idea was to start the TOPLAP node with a live coding session using the same rules of the Mexico City sessions, to emphasize the writing of the code in real-time.” We knew that the nine-minute *From Scratch* format would be welcoming for newcomers; it is short, so there is no need to prepare a long set, and it provokes everyone, whether beginner or seasoned live coder, to make mistakes, so it serves to level the playing field. Most importantly, though, in that first session we invented the cardinal rule for our audience:

All attendees must applaud at the end of nine minutes (remember that this is for fun).

With applause guaranteed and errors not only accepted but appreciated, the *From Scratch* format lends itself as an ideal meetup activity for people with any level of live coding experience.

3.2 TOPLAP Radio

TOPLAP Radio is an online radio program focused on the latest news and stories in the TOPLAP Barcelona community, live coding and computer music in general. Each episode talks about recent events and upcoming ones, whether organized by TOPLAP Barcelona or side projects involving members of the collective. We also talk about news from the live coding world, including technical, artistic and ethical aspects. And of course music produced with any kind of programmed code is played. Although the radio show is not intended to be educational, we try to explain the technical aspects and concepts in an understandable way for potential neophyte listeners.

In addition, whenever someone from the international TOPLAP community **comes to visit**, we invite them to the program to chat and explain their projects and life experience to us. For example, Olivia Jack and Shelly Knotts, among others, have passed through the studio. Many members of the local community have also been guests on the program.

Figure 4: Posters for the Trobades.

The radio show began during an artistic residency by Ramon Casamajó, a member of TOPLAP Barcelona, at the *Fabra i Coats* creation center, which gave him access to their online radio. The first two TOPLAP Radio programs were made there at the beginning of 2020. A short time later we were invited to produce three episodes of a program that Hangar aired, on the online community radio station *dublabs.es*⁴, and that led to us to having a dedicated time slot there from September 2021, with 2022-2023 being our second season of monthly broadcasts.

Usually presented by Roger Pibernat (aka *Loopier*) and Ramon Casamajó (aka *QBRNTHSS*) in Catalan – reflecting the reality of a local community grounded in a very specific place with its distinct language and cultural context, while simultaneously embracing an extremely diverse, global, open-minded group of people – the radio program has become a sound diary following and celebrating the evolution of the TOPLAP Barcelona community.

3.3 Trobades

Trobades is the Catalan word for “encounters,” or “meetings.” This is our title for a series of monographic interviews where one live coder asks another about their practice, the tools they use, their creative processes, motivations: all things live coding. After the interview, the invited artist performs a solo live set.

The idea was originally conceived in early 2020, shortly before the COVID pandemic hit our society. The format was to be a series of talks, where the invited artist would talk about any subject of their choice and then perform a live set.

When the *On-the-Fly* grant was awarded by the European Commission’s Creative Europe Programme, we were still ruled by many social restrictions, making it impossible to host in-person audiences for the talks, so we transformed it into a streaming event on our YouTube channel⁵, as we had done with all our other activities since lockdown began. We improvised a humble but cozy television studio, and aired our first show on September 3, 2020, featuring Niklas Reppel and his *Mégra* live coding language and Citlali Hernández’s work on *Coded Distance*. The show was hosted by Iván Paz.

In the four sessions of the first season, eight artists performed and shared their knowledge and live coding insights. The experience was so well-received that we have repeated it yearly, inviting live coders of all kinds, levels and backgrounds, and we intend to continue doing so. It’s an effective way to foster the knowledge exchange that live coding predicates, and provides practitioners with a platform to showcase their work and learn from each other.

Through these *Trobades*, we’ve opened a window into the minds and the work of many artists, such as Alicia Champlin, Linalab, Iván Paz, Ramón Casamajó (a.k.a. *QBRNTHSS*), Toni Jaume, Glen Fraser, Julia Múgica, Chigüire, Nicolas Lodigiani, Aristidez Rodríguez, r.phlux, Olivia Jack, Gabriel Millán, Alfonsofonso, Eloi el Bon Noi, Diego Villaseñor, Shawn Lawson, Jaime Lobato and Roger Pibernat.

3.4 Workshops

Sharing knowledge is an important part of any live coding community (or any DIY community, in fact), and, to quote Olivia Jack, workshops are also a kind of performance. To that end, we have hosted frequent workshops on a variety of topics since the inception of TOPLAP Barcelona. We tried to balance beginner-level workshops in more well-known languages with more advanced workshops, as well as workshops on **locally-developed systems** that serve as a platform for the developers to present their work and receive feedback.

Local members presented workshops on a wide variety of systems and topics, such as *Mégra* (Niklas Reppel), *Bacalao* (Glen Fraser), Binaural Live Coding (Niklas Reppel/Glen Fraser/Tim Schmele), *Superfm* and *Živa* (Roger Pibernat), *Fox-Dot* (Alberaan), *Orca* (Toni J), *TidalCycles* (Eloi el Bon Noi) and many more.

Guest workshops by well-known live coders (and original system developers), such as Alex McLean, Olivia Jack and Shelly Knotts, brought external inspiration to the community.

⁴<https://dublabs.es/shows/toplap>

⁵<https://www.youtube.com/c/TOPLAPBARCELONA>

Some of these workshops, as they happened during the pandemic, were streamed on our YouTube channel⁶ and are preserved as artifacts of that time.

Performing with a Virtual Agent was a series of workshops organized by Anna Xambó during 2021, including a collaboration with *L'Ull Cec* and *TOPLAP Barcelona*⁷. These workshops explored the possibilities of using machine learning to create virtual agents able to filter the material available at the *Freesound* platform. The models can be controlled and trained via live coding. Live coding sessions performed at the end of the workshop can be found at the project page⁸.

The latest workshop series at the end of 2022 took place in Canódrom⁹, again with one day dedicated to local developments and one dedicated to beginners in *TidalCycles* (Lina Bautista) and *Hydra* (Citlali Hernández).

3.5 Residencies

Our residency as a collective at Hangar was a great opportunity that, besides providing a venue for events, helped members and organizers develop skills, grow and refine the local live coding scene. Thanks to several collaborations and projects, in particular the *On-the-Fly* project, we were able to host several residencies. Live coding artists from other communities and parts of the world, including Shelly Knotts, Olivia Jack, Jack Armitage, Emilio Ocelotl and Marianne Teixido were able to advance their projects during their stay in Barcelona. With their residencies came the invitation to participate in our ongoing activities, such as being interviewed in a *Trobada* or contributing to a *TOPLAP Radio* episode, bringing inspiration and other perspectives to the local community.

3.6 Concerts

While the *From Scratch* meetups are the most frequent of our concert series, they are not the only one. TOPLAP Barcelona hosts two to three *algoraves* a year, occasionally as part of bigger events (for example as part of the *Ars Electronica Garden* in 2020¹⁰). As somewhat of a counterpoint to the *algorave* format, the *Algobiente* series, which gives live coders the chance to play more ambient music at a slower pace, and on an 8-channel setup, had its fourth edition in 2022.

Notable one-off events in the past were TOPLAP Barcelona's involvement in the Zeppelin Festival in 2019, contributions to the *Rarefacció* festival¹¹, and the delegations that played at the ESC festival¹² in rural Catalonia.

3.7 VIU

VIU is a live coding festival held annually, lasting four or five days and featuring workshops, concerts, demos, and other activities dedicated to live coding practice.

VIU has two main objectives, the first being to gather the local community and to connect its members mutually, as well as with international guests, in order to exchange methodologies, tools, and experiences. The second objective is to present live coding to the general public, so the community can grow as the practice reaches new audiences.

So far, the festival has taken place at Hangar, the art centre where TOPLAP Barcelona was based for the past four years.

The first edition of VIU¹³ was held from January 21 to 25, 2019, right after the fourth ICLC conference. Over five days we organized three workshops, seven demos, a roundtable, three performances, two *From Scratch* sessions, and an *algorave*, in collaboration with live coders from all over the world who had travelled to Barcelona after Madrid's ICLC.

The second VIU took place from February 13 to 16, 2020¹⁴. This edition was focused on developing and strengthening our local community with a *From Scratch* marathon, two workshops, a *Calçotada* (a *typical catalan spring feast*), and an *algorave*.

In 2021, VIU was held from March 24 to 27¹⁵. This edition started with the presentation of our *Down The Rabbit Hole*¹⁶ album, an introductory workshop, a round table, a *From Scratch* session, and an *algorave*.

⁶<https://www.youtube.com/c/TOPLAPBARCELONA>

⁷<https://mirlca.dmu.ac.uk/>

⁸<https://sonar.es/en/2022/news/sonar-and-on-the-fly-present-algorave>

⁹<https://canodrom.barcelona/>

¹⁰<https://ars.electronica.art/keplersgardens/de/algorave/>

¹¹2021: <https://hangar.org/en/audio-formal/rarefaccio4/> 2022: <https://hangar.org/es/audio-formal/rarefaccio-2022/>

¹²<https://escape.cat/>

¹³<https://toplapbarcelona.hangar.org/index.php/viu-en/>

¹⁴<https://toplapbarcelona.hangar.org/index.php/viu2020/>

¹⁵<https://toplapbarcelona.hangar.org/index.php/viu2021/>

¹⁶<https://callitanythingrecords.bandcamp.com/album/down-the-rabbit-hole>

Figure 5: New t-shirts after VIU Algorave 2020.

The fourth edition was held from March 24 to 27, 2022¹⁷, and once more we were able to welcome international guests and offer workshops, demos, an experimental concert, and, of course, *From Scratch* and algorave sessions.

This year VIU will celebrate its 5th edition, from April 27 to 30. At the time of this writing the program is unknown, but this edition will certainly be part of the satellite events of ICLC 2023.

3.8 On-the-Fly

On-the-Fly was a project to promote live coding practice by supporting knowledge exchange between communities, engaging with critical reflections, promoting free and open source tools and introducing live coding to new audiences.

This project, co-founded by the Creative Europe program, was led by Hangar as an institution and TOPLAP Barcelona as the content creator, with Lina Bautista and Iván Paz as artistic directors, in collaboration with ZKM | Center for Art and Media Karlsruhe, Ljudmila and Creative Coding Utrecht with Live Coding Netherlands (NLCL) support.

The project had a duration of two years from October 2020 through September 2022, during which the TOPLAP Barcelona community had the opportunity to mature and grow. Thanks to the *On-the-Fly* residencies, Shelly Knotts, Olivia Jack, and Jack Armitage developed part of their projects in Barcelona and exchanged their expertise and knowledge with the local community. Several events took place thanks to the project, such as *Proxy Space*¹⁸, the *Sonar Algorave*¹⁹, the Barcelona Node of the *Algorithmic Art Assembly*²⁰, and the *on-the-fly.collect()*²¹ event, that included several workshops, concerts, and collaborations.

3.9 Technical Developments

Apart from being **fairly polyglot in general**, both in spoken/human and programmed/computer languages, there's an active subset of the community that develops their own live coding systems. From domain-specific languages embedded in SuperCollider, such as Glen Fraser's *Bacalao* or *Živa* by Roger Pibernat aka Loopier (developed during his residency in Ljubljana), to visual or audio-visual environments, such as the browser-based *lalluvia* by Alfonso Pardo, to standalone developments such as *Mégra* by Niklas Reppel, the community has spawned plenty of new approaches, experiments, and tools. This means, there are new things and a plethora of languages to observe at any TOPLAP Barcelona event. It's also worth mentioning that it's not only people with software development backgrounds who have developed and maintained their own environments.

Projects:

- Animatron (Glen Fraser + Roger Pibernat): <https://github.com/loopier/animatron>
- Bacalao (Glen Fraser): <https://github.com/totalgee/bacalao>
- lalluvia (Alfonso Fonso): <https://www.lalluvia.com/>
- Mégra (Niklas Reppel): <https://github.com/the-drunk-coder/megra.rs>
- SuperFM synth for SuperDirt (Roger Pibernat)
- Živa (Roger Pibernat): <https://github.com/loopier/ziva>
- RuLer (Iván Paz): <https://github.com/musikinformatik/exploring-parameters>

¹⁷<https://toplapbarcelona.hangar.org/>

¹⁸<https://hangar.org/en/activitats-recerca-i-transferencia-de-coneixements/proxyspace/>

¹⁹<https://sonar.es/en/2022/news/sonar-and-on-the-fly-present-algorave>

²⁰<https://onthe-fly.space/read/algorithmic-art-assembly-aaa>

²¹<https://onthe-fly.space/read/on-the-fly-collect>

4 Community Voices

A community wouldn't be anything without its members. In this report, many people have been mentioned, but that only represents a small part of the community, so we collected some voices from other community members.

The community welcomed me with much love. The environment in its wide sense, the tools we work with, the knowledge we share. All those features make it a kind of 'oasis', an ideal place to create. In my particular case, it represents the ideal place for my work to be manifested in its entirety.

- Maia Francisco (<https://maiafrancisco.com/>)

TOPLAP is a bunch of "little weirdos" making annoying sounds with their laptops, pretending futuristic music that seems way ahead of our time, our comprehension and our dance moves ...
Pero los queremos. Regalo y legado del algoritmo.

- Alfonso Pardo aka *Alfonsofonso* (<https://www.lalluvia.com/>)

TOPLAP Barcelona is a very generous space, as well as talented. It was difficult for me to arrive in the city just before the pandemic and TOPLAP was a space that opened its doors to me, invited me to participate and be part of the collective. TOPLAP Barcelona is much more than the 'clic-clic-clic' noise of the keyboards.

- NICO AKA PICANTE

TOPLAP Barcelona has an altruistic disposition aimed at sharing knowledge and experiences for the direct benefit of those who are interested in and practice the Live Coding technique and all its collaborative aspects with other disciplines within the universe of digital arts.

- Gabriel Millán (<https://youtube.com/@doyourownwaves4214>)

I would like to highlight the role of the "From Scratch" sessions that have been held without fail every last Thursday of the month. Neither the pandemic nor the end of the Hangar residency, to name a few of the setbacks we have had to deal with, have managed to prevent us from meeting up to share our blank screens. I think that the "From Scratch" sessions are a fundamental, almost core event, unavoidable for any future TOPLAP community that wants to initiate a process similar to the one we have undertaken in Barcelona.

- Eloi el Bon Noi (<https://www.instagram.com/eloielbonnoi/>)

TOPLAP Barcelona es un grupo de personas a las que admiro profundamente y con quienes he compartido grandes experiencias. Gracias a ellos decidí dar el paso a experimentar con la improvisación y el código, a tener confianza con ello y especialmente a no tener miedo a los errores de los directos.

(TOPLAP Barcelona is a group of people whom I deeply admire and with whom I have shared great experiences. Thanks to them I decided to take the step and experiment with improvisation and code, to be confident with it and especially not to be afraid of the mistakes when playing live.)

- Citlali Hernández aka *Turbulente* (<https://turbulente.net/>)

References

Villasenor, Hernani, and Iván Paz. 2020. "Live Coding from Scratch: The Cases of Practice in Mexico City and Barcelona." In *International Conference on Live Coding 2020*.